

**Surgical tactics for combined chest and abdominal injuries in the
context of preventing postoperative bronchopulmonary complications
(literature review)**

**Mustafakulov I.B.¹, Norov M.Ch.², Tohirov Sh.M.³, Choriev Kh.K.³, Djurayeva
Z.A.^{1,4}, Shakirov B.M.^{1,5}**

¹ Department of Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand,
Uzbekistan.

² Department of Surgery, Kashkadarya region of Hospital, Kashkadarya, Uzbekistan

³ Department of Surgery, Termez branch of Tashkent Medical University,
Surkhandarya Region, Uzbekistan.

⁴ Department of Endocrinology, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand,
Uzbekistan.

⁵ Burn department of Centre of Emergency Medical Care, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

Abstract.

Combined thoracoabdominal injuries represent one of the most severe forms of trauma and are associated with high mortality and a substantial incidence of postoperative complications. This narrative review analyzes current concepts of the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying bronchopulmonary complications in combined thoracoabdominal trauma and examines the evolution of surgical tactics and choice of operative approach from a preventive perspective. Modern strategies for the prevention of bronchopulmonary complications based on the integration of surgical and intensive care approaches and early risk stratification are discussed.

Keywords: Combined trauma; Diagnostics, Thoracoabdominal injuries; Surgical tactics.

Introduction

Combined injuries of the chest and abdominal organs represent one of the most severe forms of traumatic damage, associated with high mortality and a significant frequency of complications, primarily affecting the respiratory system [1,2]. The clinical significance of this category of injuries is determined not only by the severity of anatomical damage but also by pronounced clinical polymorphism, symptom competition, and a high likelihood of diagnostic and tactical errors [3]. Despite advances in emergency surgical techniques, anesthetic support, and intensive care, postoperative pulmonary complications continue to occupy a leading position among unfavorable outcomes, influencing the duration of mechanical ventilation, length of stay in the intensive care unit, and overall hospital mortality [4,5].

According to recent studies, up to 15% of fatalities in combined thoracoabdominal trauma occur in patients who did not have injuries that were objectively incompatible with life [6]. These points to the key role of factors such as timing, diagnostic delays, errors in choosing surgical tactics, and insufficient prevention of postoperative complications [7]. In this regard, analyzing modern approaches to the surgical treatment of combined thoracoabdominal injuries closely linked with the issue of bronchopulmonary complications and their prevention, is a relevant task in emergency and trauma surgery.

Pathophysiological mechanisms of bronchopulmonary complications in combined thoracoabdominal injuries. The development of bronchopulmonary complications in combined chest and abdominal injuries is a multifactorial process caused by both direct damage to the respiratory structures and systemic disorders that develop in response to severe trauma. The leading role is played by impaired ventilation-perfusion ratios, which occur due to lung parenchymal damage, pronounced pain syndrome, restricted chest and diaphragm excursion, as well as the development of intra-abdominal hypertension [8-10]. These changes are accompanied by reduced alveolar ventilation, increased intrapulmonary shunting, and progressive hypoxemia.

Hemorrhagic shock and trauma-induced coagulopathy play a key role in the development of microcirculatory disorders in lung tissue. Impaired rheological properties of blood, endothelial dysfunction, and activation of the systemic inflammatory response led to increased permeability of the alveolocapillary membrane, interstitial and alveolar edema, and the formation of diffuse alveolar damage [11,12]. These processes underlie the development of atelectasis, secondary bacterial colonization of the airways, and acute respiratory distress syndrome [13].

Diaphragm injuries play a special role in the pathogenesis of respiratory disorders and often remain undiagnosed until surgery in a significant proportion of patients [7–9,30]. Even small diaphragm defects lead to a disruption of the synchrony of respiratory movements, a decrease in negative intrathoracic pressure, and impaired venous return. Paradoxical movements of the diaphragmatic domes and its functional insufficiency are accompanied by a pronounced reduction in the functional residual capacity of the lungs and the formation of basal atelectasis [14-15].

In combination with abdominal organ injuries, diaphragmatic defects create conditions for the migration of air, blood, and infected contents into the pleural cavity, significantly increasing the risk of pleural empyema, pneumonia, and the progression of respiratory failure [16]. Intra-abdominal hypertension also has additional significance, as it mechanically restricts diaphragmatic movement and exacerbates ventilatory disorders [17,18].

Surgical strategy and choice of access as factors in the prevention of bronchopulmonary complications. The choice of surgical strategy in combined thoracoabdominal injuries is one of the key factors determining the frequency and severity of postoperative bronchopulmonary complications. Historically, the widespread use of diagnostic thoracotomies and laparotomies was accompanied by a high incidence of respiratory complications due to significant surgical trauma and pronounced disruption of respiratory mechanics [19]. Extensive chest wall incisions increase pain, limit chest wall excursion, reduce the effectiveness of the cough reflex and mucociliary clearance, thereby creating conditions for hypoventilation and pulmonary congestion [20,21].

At the same time, an excessively wait-and-see approach when underestimating the severity of the condition and competing injuries leads to the progression of shock, respiratory failure, and systemic inflammatory response, which also significantly increases the risk of bronchopulmonary complications [22,23]. In cases of combined trauma, the clinical manifestations of chest and abdominal injuries often mask each other, complicating timely tactical decision-making and increasing the likelihood of diagnostic errors.

Modern concepts of surgical treatment emphasize the need to prioritize the elimination of life-threatening conditions with the minimal possible surgical trauma. Thoracotomy is indicated in cases of massive hemothorax, cardiac tamponade, and tension pneumothorax, as it allows for rapid restoration of adequate oxygenation and hemodynamics, preventing the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome [24,25]. Laparotomy in cases of predominant abdominal injury helps to relieve intra-abdominal hypertension and improve diaphragmatic

excursion, which is fundamentally important for the prevention of respiratory complications [26].

Mandatory drainage of the pleural cavity, even in cases of minimal hemopneumothorax, prior to general anesthesia is considered a crucial preventive measure, allowing the prevention of intraoperative tension pneumothorax and a sudden deterioration of lung ventilation [27].

Minimally invasive technologies in the prevention of bronchopulmonary complications. The introduction of endoscopic surgical technologies has significantly changed the approaches to the treatment of combined thoracoabdominal injuries. Video-assisted thoracoscopy allows for the effective evacuation of hemothorax, the repair of lung injuries, and the prevention of residual pleural cavity formation, which is accompanied by a reliable reduction in the incidence of bronchopulmonary complications [28,29]. Video-assisted laparoscopy provides high diagnostic accuracy for injuries of the abdominal organs and diaphragm with minimal impact on respiratory mechanics [30].

The use of minimally invasive methods is associated with a reduction in the duration of mechanical ventilation, decreased need for analgesic sedation, and shorter stays in the intensive care unit [31]. Thus, endoscopic surgery is considered not only as a diagnostic and therapeutic tool but also as an important element in the prevention of postoperative respiratory complications.

Postoperative intensive care and ventilator-dependent bronchopulmonary complications. The postoperative period in patients with combined thoracoabdominal injuries is characterized by a high incidence of respiratory disorders, which necessitates prolonged stays in the intensive care unit and the use of mechanical ventilation. According to the literature, 40 to 70% of patients in this category require postoperative mechanical ventilation, with the duration of ventilatory support directly correlating with the severity of the injury, the extent of surgical intervention, and the intensity of the systemic inflammatory response [32-34].

Prolonged mechanical ventilation is considered an independent risk factor for the development of pulmonary complications, including ventilator-associated pneumonia, barotrauma, polytrauma, as well as respiratory muscle dysfunction [35]. In patients with combined trauma, these complications develop against the background of initial lung parenchymal damage, microcirculatory disorders, and disruptions in central respiratory regulation.

Diaphragmatic dysfunction acquires particular significance, developing both as a result of direct traumatic injury and as a consequence of prolonged mechanical ventilation, deep sedation, and the use of muscle relaxants [36]. Diaphragmatic weakness is one of the leading

causes of unsuccessful weaning from mechanical ventilation and reintubation, which, in turn, increases the risk of developing hospital-acquired pneumonia [37].

Ventilator-associated pneumonia as a key factor in adverse outcomes. Ventilator-associated pneumonia occupies a central place in the spectrum of postoperative bronchopulmonary complications in patients with combined thoracoabdominal trauma. According to various studies, its incidence ranges from 25% to 45%, and in the group of patients with severe chest trauma and diaphragmatic injury, it can exceed 50% [38]. The development of VAP is significantly associated with an increased duration of mechanical ventilation, longer stays in the intensive care unit, and higher hospital mortality.

The pathogenesis of ventilator-associated pneumonia in this patient category has several distinctive features. Impairment of the cough reflex, aspiration of gastric contents, reduced mucociliary clearance, and colonization of the tracheobronchial tree by hospital flora create conditions for rapid infection of the lower respiratory tract [39]. Systemic immunosuppression, which develops against the background of severe trauma, massive transfusion therapy, and systemic inflammatory response, also plays an additional role [40].

A particularly unfavorable factor is the combination of ventilator-associated pneumonia with acute respiratory distress syndrome, which is often observed in patients with extensive chest injuries and prolonged hypoxia in the early postoperative period [41]. In such cases, mortality reaches extremely high levels, and the possibilities for correcting respiratory disorders are significantly limited.

Anesthetic and ventilatory strategies for the prevention of bronchopulmonary complications. Modern approaches to anesthetic management of patients with combined thoracoabdominal injuries focus on minimizing the negative impact of surgical and ventilatory factors on the respiratory system. The use of protective lung ventilation with limitations on tidal volume, plateau pressure, and an adequate level of positive end-expiratory pressure is considered a key element in the prevention of polytrauma [42].

The literature emphasizes the importance of an early transition to spontaneous breathing modes and the gradual reduction of ventilatory support, which allows for a decrease in diaphragmatic dysfunction and a reduction in the duration of mechanical ventilation [43]. Adequate multimodal analgesia, including regional techniques, promotes the restoration of effective breathing and reduces the risk of hypoventilation and pulmonary congestion.

Particular attention should be given to the issue of sedation. Deep and prolonged sedation is associated with an increased incidence of ventilator-associated pneumonia, delirium,

and respiratory muscle weakness [44]. Consequently, modern protocols recommend the use of the minimal necessary sedation with a daily assessment of the possibility of its reduction.

Predictive models and risk stratification of bronchopulmonary complications. In recent years, the literature has actively discussed the need for early risk stratification of bronchopulmonary complications in patients with combined thoracoabdominal injuries. The use of prognostic models based on clinical, laboratory, and instrumental indicators allows for the individualization of surgical and intensive care strategies [45].

The most informative predictors of severe respiratory complications are considered to be the degree of hemorrhagic shock, lactate level, coagulopathy indicators, severity of chest injuries, and the presence of diaphragmatic defects [46]. Biomarkers of systemic inflammation and lung injury, which allow the identification of high-risk patients even before the clinical manifestation of complications, also have significant prognostic value [47].

The integration of data from predictive models into clinical treatment algorithms allows for the optimization of surgical access selection, the extent of intervention, and the strategy for postoperative intensive care, reducing the incidence of bronchopulmonary complications and improving treatment outcomes.

Conclusion.

Thus, combined injuries of the chest and abdominal organs represent an extremely complex clinical and surgical problem, where the outcome of treatment is largely determined not only by the anatomical severity of the injuries but also by the rationale behind surgical and resuscitative strategies. Postoperative bronchopulmonary complications, including ventilator-associated pneumonia, remain one of the leading causes of unfavorable outcomes in this patient population.

A comprehensive analysis of the current literature indicates the need to integrate rational surgical approaches, minimally invasive technologies, protective ventilation strategies, and early risk stratification. Only a systematic, interdisciplinary approach allows for a significant reduction in the incidence of respiratory complications, a decrease in the duration of mechanical ventilation, and an improvement in survival among patients with combined thoracoabdominal trauma.

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